

Numerical simulation of electrochemical systems by coupling analytical calculation of the diffuse double layer and finite element description of solution bulk

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Abstract:

Numerical modelling of electrochemical systems covers length scales from the nanometers up to the macroscopic scale. With finite element methods, the mesh must be extremely fine to describe the diffuse double layer, thus increasing the needed computational resources. We propose a method to describe the diffuse double layer by analytical equations, expressed as boundary conditions for the partial differential equations describing the solution bulk. We apply the method to a one-dimensional system, i.e. to a cell with plane parallel electrodes, in the presence of a redox couple and a supporting electrolyte. We provide evidence of the precision of the method.

Keywords: Electrical Double Layer, Finite Element Methods, Impedance, Analytical solutions

1 Introduction

Electrochemistry plays a central role in modern science and engineering, due to the increasing demand for energy storage and conversion methods, such as batteries, supercapacitors, and fuel cells. The improvement and the optimization of the technology is often aided by the mathematical modelling of the electrochemical systems and by the numerical solution of the resulting partial differential equations. A remarkable feature of electrochemical systems is the simultaneous presence of various physical phenomena, occurring at different time and space scales. Electron transfer, possibly through tunnelling, hydration sphere dynamics, and adsorption take place at atomic and molecular scale. Charge screening leads to the formation of the electric double layer (EDL), with a diffuse double layer (DDL) extending on a length of the order of nanometers [1,2]. Together, the electron transfer resistance and the EDL capacitance form a circuit with a characteristic response time of the order of 1 ms or less. At larger space and time scale, the system is dominated by molecule diffusion and migration, ranging up to the macroscopic size of the device and decay times of the order of seconds or more. The geometry of the system also involves multiple scales, ranging from the molecular scale of nanoporous materials to the macroscopic scale of the electrode and separator assembly. The wide range of involved space- and time-scales is reflected by the features occurring on a wide range of frequencies in electrochemical impedance spectroscopy [2,3].

The partial differential equations describing the model are often solved by finite element methods [4,5]. However, due to the presence of a so wide range of spatial scales, the approach is expensive in terms of required computational resources: the mesh must be extremely fine in the region of the DDL and must be smoothly adapted to the mesh describing the solution bulk and the electrode geometry, at macroscopic spatial scale. In this paper, we propose a method for decreasing the needed computational resources, based on the observation that the DDL is usually at thermodynamic equilibrium with a thin layer of solution near the electrode. This fact allows us to analytically solve the equations in the region of the DDL, looking for equilibrium solutions. The analytical solution is then imposed as a boundary condition for the partial differential equations describing the bulk, solved by means of finite element methods. This gives rise to a semi-analytical method, with reduced computational resource consumption with respect to the purely numerical one.

The analytical solution method is inspired by the Gouy-Chapman-Stern theory, but it is extended to the case of a redox couple with a supporting electrolyte, i.e., to the case of more than two ion species. Analytical solutions can be easily found for specific combinations of ion charges. The traditional Gouy-Chapman-Stern theory is usually developed for two ion species, with equal and opposite charges $z_p = -z_n$. We extend to the case of a redox couple with charges $z_{Red} = 0$ and $z_{Ox} = 1$, and a supporting electrolyte with ion charges $z_p = 1$ and $z_n = -1$. These charges correspond, e.g., to

the case of ferrocene / ferrocenium redox couple [6] with potassium fluoride supporting electrolyte. Extension to different charges is also possible.

The example of application of the method is to an electrochemical cell with two plane and infinite parallel electrodes; the system is assumed to be invariant under translation along the planes, thus the partial differential equations only depend on one spatial coordinate (the system is one-dimensional). Under quite general assumptions, the analytical solution of the equations in the DDL region is intrinsically one-dimensional: this happens if, together with the assumption that the DDL is at thermodynamic equilibrium, we additionally assume that the electrode surface is locally flat and the variations of solution properties along the electrode surface take place on length scales much longer than the DDL thickness. It is thus possible to use the (one-dimensional) analytical solution in combination with two- or three-dimensional descriptions of the macroscopic system, solved by finite element methods.

2 Description of the physical model

Fig. 1: sketch of the electrochemical system and definition of the domains.

The physical model is described in detail in Ref. [4] and it is sketched in Fig. 1. A solution fills the space between two identical, flat, and parallel electrodes, arbitrarily considered as working- and counter-electrode. The electrodes are assumed to be infinite, as an approximation of a large aspect ratio cell; the dependence of the dynamic variables of the model on space is thus one-dimensional.

The solution contains a redox couple, formed by Red and Ox species, and a supporting electrolyte. The concentrations of the reduced and oxidized species and of the cation and anion of the supporting electrolyte are called C_{red} , C_{ox} , C_K , and C_F (the

meaning of the subscripts F and K are clear when thinking of potassium fluoride as supporting electrolyte). The dynamic variables of the system are these four concentrations, C_{red} , C_{ox} , C_K , and C_F , and the electrical potential φ .

The space in the cell is divided into five regions, as shown in Fig. 1. The layers close to the electrodes are the Stern layers, delimited by the electrode surface and the outer Helmholtz planes (OHP), having thickness d_{OHP} ; in these layers, the concentrations of all the molecules vanish, because the distance from the solid electrode surface is less than the minimum approach distance. The ions are allowed to move in the other three regions (domains I, II, and III), which are described below. The axis of the coordinate x is perpendicular to the electrode surface and its origin is arbitrarily set to the OHP of the working electrode. The cell thickness, i.e. the distance between the working- and counter-electrode, is L . Otherwise noted, the following description refers to the working electrode; equivalent equations hold for the counter-electrode.

The redox reaction $Ox^+ + e^- \rightarrow Red$ takes place near the electrodes; according to Butler-Volmer equation, the reaction rates r_{ox} and r_{red} (production of Ox and Red species, respectively) are:

$$r_{ox} = -k_{red}C_{ox} + k_{ox}C_{red} \quad (1)$$

$$r_{red} = -k_{ox}C_{red} + k_{red}C_{ox} \quad (2)$$

where k_{ox} and k_{red} are the rate constants for Ox and Red components, respectively. We assume that, due to tunnelling, the reactions take place in a finite volume, outside the OHP; thus r_{ox} , r_{red} , k_{ox} , and k_{red} are finite (not vanishing) for x values close to 0. The rate constants are defined as:

$$k_{ox}(x) = k^0 \exp(-\beta x) \exp \left\{ -\alpha \frac{F[\varphi(x) - \varphi_M - \Delta\varphi_0]}{RT} \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$k_{red}(x) = k^0 \exp(-\beta x) \exp \left\{ (1 - \alpha) \frac{F[\varphi(x) - \varphi_M - \Delta\varphi_0]}{RT} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where $\varphi_M = \varphi(-d_{OHP})$ is the potential of the electrode, k^0 is the standard electron transfer rate, β is the inverse of the tunnelling distance, α is the transfer coefficient, F is the Faraday constant, R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature and $\Delta\varphi_0$ is the standard potential of the redox reaction. We assume that the electrode is passive, i.e. it does not take part to the redox reaction.

In domains I, II, and III, the concentrations C_i are governed by the Nernst-Planck equations, which describe the diffusion and migration phenomena:

$$\frac{dC_i}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i + r_i \quad (5)$$

where r_{ox} and r_{red} are the reaction rates defined in Eqs. 1 and 2, while r_K and r_F vanish; the fluxes \mathbf{J}_i are defined as:

$$\mathbf{J}_i = D_i \nabla C_i + \frac{D_i z_i F C_i}{RT} \nabla \varphi \quad (6)$$

where the subscript i refers to the i -th ion, C_i is the concentration, D_i is the diffusion coefficient, z_i is the ion charge expressed in electron charge unit. The boundary conditions on the OHP is the vanishing of the fluxes \mathbf{J}_i ; in particular:

$$\mathbf{J}_i(x = 0) = 0 \quad (7)$$

In the whole system (i.e., the Stern layers and the three domains), the Poisson equation holds:

$$\frac{d^2\varphi}{dx^2} = -\frac{\rho}{\varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0} \quad (8)$$

where ε_0 is the permittivity of vacuum, ε_r is the relative permittivity, and the charge density ρ is:

$$\rho = F \sum_i z_i C_i \quad (9)$$

The relative permittivity ε_r has different values in the Stern layer and in the bulk [7]; we assume the values 10 and 72 for the Stern layer and for the bulk, respectively. In

our model, the value of ε_r in the Stern layer only affects the capacitance of the Stern layer, so its increase has the same effect of a decrease of the Stern layer thickness, d_{OHP} .

The solution bulk is represented by Domain II. The domains I and III represent the region in which the DDL is present, i.e. where the charge neutrality is significantly violated. The same equations hold in these three domains and continuity is assumed at the boundaries 1 and 2 (see Fig. 1). The thickness of the domains I and III, called d_{DDL} , is chosen so that the DDL and the tunnelling are limited to domains I and III. This is achieved by choosing d_{DDL} as the maximum between $10/\beta$ and 10λ , where β is the above-described inverse of the tunnelling distance and λ is the Debye length, the characteristic length of the DDL, given by:

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0}{F^2 \sum_i C_{i,0} z_i^2}} \quad (10)$$

In our work, d_{ddl} is less than 30 nm for all the simulations, thus it is orders of magnitude smaller than the overall cell thickness.

In Sect. (III) we will show that the domain I can be approximately handled by analytical expressions (an analogous treatment holds for domain III).

The electrode potentials E_{WE} and E_{CE} of the working and counter electrodes, respectively, are calculated as the difference between the potential φ at the electrode surface and the potential in a point in the centre of the cell; for the working electrode: $E_{WE} = \varphi_M - \varphi(x = L/2)$.

According to the model described so far, the potential of zero charge, i.e. the value of E_{WE} for which the EDL of the working electrode is completely discharged, is $E_{WE} = 0$. This is an arbitrary choice, which depends on the actually chosen reference electrode and can be further modified by the solvent polarization effects induced by the interactions between the electrode surface and the solvent and by the possible

presence of permanent charges on the surface. We do not model such phenomena; the electrode potentials E_{WE} and E_{CE} are thus measured with reference to the potential of zero charge of the chosen electrodes.

The current density i has two terms, a Faradaic one representing the redox reaction and a capacitive one, due to the variation of the charge accumulated in the EDL:

$$i(t) = F \int_I r_{ox} dx - \frac{d}{dt} \int_I \rho dx \quad (11)$$

where the integration range refers to domain I.

Table.1. List of the physical parameters of the model

Parameter	Value	Definition
D_F	$1.48 \times 10^{-9} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$	Diffusion coefficient of negative ion of supporting electrolyte (fluoride ion)
D_K	$1.96 \times 10^{-9} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$	Diffusion coefficient of positive ion of supporting electrolyte (potassium)
D_{ox}	$2.60 \times 10^{-9} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$	Diffusion coefficient of oxidized species (ferrocenium)
D_{red}	$2.60 \times 10^{-9} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$	Diffusion coefficient of reduced species (ferrocene)
L	100 μm	Distance between electrodes
T	300 K	Temperature
d_{OHP}	0.5 nm	Length of outer Helmholtz layer
k_0	$1.00 \times 10^6 \text{1/s}$	Reaction constant
z_F	-1	Charge of supporting electrolyte negative ion (fluoride)
z_K	+1	Charge of supporting electrolyte positive ion (potassium)
z_{ox}	+1	Charge of oxidized species (ferrocenium)
z_{red}	0	Charge of reduced species (ferrocene)
$\Delta\phi_0$	0.0 V	Standard potential of the redox reaction
α	0.5	Transfer coefficient
β	$3.33 \times 10^9 \text{1/m}$	Inverse of the tunnelling distance
ϵ_r	72	Relative permittivity in bulk
ϵ_r	10	Relative permittivity in Stern layer

Summarizing, the dynamic variables of the numerical model are the concentrations C_i , with the subscript i taking the values Red, Ox, K, F, and the potential φ . The physical parameters of the model are given in Table 1 and the other symbols defined in the numerical model are summarized in Supporting Information, Sect. S1, Table S1.

3 Semi-analytical model

The novel result reported in this paper is a semi-analytical mathematical model which gives results very close to the ones of the model described in the previous section. In this semi-analytical model, explicit expressions for the dynamic variables in domain I are calculated, so that the behaviour of the EDL is mathematically described by means of an additional dynamic variable and some boundary conditions on boundary 1. The numerical solution of equations in domain I is thus no more needed; this simplification significantly decreases the computational resources needed for the overall calculation, since the domain I must be split into a very large number of elements in order to properly describe the DDL.

A similar approach has been already reported for the more simple case of a solution of salt that dissociate into two ions with opposite charges, in the absence of redox reactions; this approach has been also used to model porous materials [8]. Here, we extend the approach to the presence of redox reactions, a much more complex case.

Although the model reported in the previous section and the numerical calculation work for any combination of charges z_{red} , z_{ox} , z_F , and z_K , the semi-analytical method is developed for a particular combination of ion charges: $z_{red} = 0$, $z_{ox} = 1$, $z_F = -1$, $z_K = 1$. This is the case of ferrocene – ferrocenium redox couple, with, e.g., potassium fluoride as supporting electrolyte.

3.1 Neglecting the tunnelling

The first simplification consists in neglecting the tunnelling, i.e. in assuming that the chemical reaction takes place exactly on the OHP. This approximation holds for $\beta \ll \lambda$. Eq. 5 thus becomes:

$$\frac{dC_i}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i \quad (12)$$

i.e. all the r_i vanish in the volume, while the reaction rates appear in the boundary conditions on the mass fluxes:

$$\mathbf{J}_i(x = 0) = G_i \mathbf{n} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the unit vector pointing along the x axis and the surface reaction rates G_i represent the integral of the reaction rates over x in boundary I:

$$G_i = \int_I r_i(x) dx \quad (14)$$

The supporting electrolyte does not take part into the reaction, thus $G_F = G_K = 0$; moreover $G_{red} = -G_{ox}$. The latter can be calculated using Eqs. 1 and 14:

$$G_{ox} = \int_I [-k_{red}(x)C_{ox}(x) + k_{ox}(x)C_{red}(x)] dx \quad (15)$$

In turn, k_{red} and k_{ox} are expressed using Eqs. 3 and 4:

$$G_{ox} = \int_I k_0 \exp(-\beta x) \left(-C_{ox}(x) \exp\left\{-\alpha \frac{1}{RT} F[\varphi(x) - \varphi_M - \Delta\varphi_0]\right\} + C_{red}(x) \exp\left\{(1 - \alpha) \frac{1}{RT} F[\varphi(x) - \varphi_M - \Delta\varphi_0]\right\} \right) dx \quad (16)$$

As an approximation, we assume that the first exponential (having decay length of $1/\beta$), decays much faster than the following two (having decay length λ , which represents the characteristic length scale of the DDL). We can thus approximate the last two exponentials with their constant value in $x = 0$ and integrate the first:

$$G_{ox} = k_0 \frac{1 - \exp(-\beta d_{DDL})}{\beta}$$

$$\left(-C_{ox}(x = 0) \exp \left\{ -\alpha \frac{1}{RT} F[\varphi(x = 0) - \varphi_M - \Delta\varphi_0] \right\} \right.$$

$$\left. + C_{red}(x = 0) \exp \left\{ (1 - \alpha) \frac{1}{RT} F[\varphi(x = 0) - \varphi_M - \Delta\varphi_0] \right\} \right) \quad (17)$$

Moreover:

$$G_{Red} = -G_{ox} \quad (18)$$

$$G_K = G_F = 0 \quad (19)$$

The validity of the approximations is verified by the numerical calculations.

3.2 Gouy-Chapman-Stern theory

A further approximation consists in assuming that the solution in domain I is always under thermodynamic equilibrium condition: since d_{DDL} is extremely short, diffusion equilibrates the ions in domain I on time scales that are much faster than diffusion and migration, which dominate the behaviour of the solution bulk. Typically, the time scales relevant for electrochemistry are longer than 1 μ s, while the diffusive time across d_{DDL} is of the order of 10 ns.

Under this approximation, we can use the Gouy-Chapman-Stern theory to describe the EDL [2]. Since we are dealing with three charged ion species, instead of the two of the traditional theory, we shortly summarize the equations to show how to handle the various ion concentrations.

Under thermodynamic equilibrium, the Boltzman distribution gives the concentration in domain I:

$$C_i(x) = \tilde{C}_i \exp \left\{ -\frac{z_i F [\varphi(x) - \tilde{\varphi}]}{RT} \right\} \quad (20)$$

where the “bulk” quantities \tilde{C}_i and $\tilde{\varphi}$ are taken at boundary 1, assumed to be far enough from the electrode to ensure charge neutrality. Following Ref. [2], the Boltzman distribution Eq. 20 and the Poisson equation 8 can be elaborated to give:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dx} \right)^2 &= \frac{2RT}{\varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0} \left\{ -[\tilde{C}_K + \tilde{C}_F + \tilde{C}_{ox}] + \tilde{C}_K \exp \left[-\frac{F[\varphi(x) - \tilde{\varphi}]}{RT} \right] \right. \\ &+ \tilde{C}_F \exp \left[\frac{F[\varphi(x) - \tilde{\varphi}]}{RT} \right] + \tilde{C}_{ox} \exp \left(-\frac{F[\varphi(x) - \tilde{\varphi}]}{RT} \right) \left. \right\} + A \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where the arbitrary constant A must be evaluated based on boundary conditions; imposing $\varphi(x) = \tilde{\varphi}$ and $\frac{d\varphi}{dx} = 0$ in the bulk, $A = 0$.

As an additional approximation, we impose the electroneutrality of the solution bulk:

$$\tilde{C}_F = \tilde{C}_K + \tilde{C}_{ox} \quad (22)$$

Equation 21 becomes:

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dx} = -\sqrt{\frac{8RT}{\varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0}} \tilde{C}_F \sinh \left(\frac{F[\varphi(x) - \tilde{\varphi}]}{2RT} \right) \quad (23)$$

We now relate this equation to the charge density at the electrode surface, σ_M , and to the charge density in the DDL, σ_S . From Gauss law, we get:

$$\varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0 \left. \frac{d\varphi}{dx} \right|_{x=0} = \sigma_M = -\sigma_S \quad (24)$$

By combining Eqs. 23 and 24, we get:

$$\varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0 \sqrt{\frac{8RT}{\varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0}} \tilde{C}_F \sinh \left(\frac{F[\varphi(x=0) - \tilde{\varphi}]}{2RT} \right) = \sigma_M = -\sigma_S \quad (25)$$

Inverting the relation:

$$\tilde{\varphi} - \varphi(x = 0) = -\frac{2RT}{F} \sinh^{-1} \left(-\frac{\sigma_S}{\sqrt{8RT\varepsilon_r\varepsilon_0\tilde{C}_F}} \right) \quad (26)$$

The potential difference between the electrode surface and the OHP can also be calculated by integrating Eq. 24, since the electric field is constant in the Stern layer:

$$\varphi_M - \varphi(x = 0) = -\frac{d_{OHP}}{\varepsilon_r\varepsilon_0} \sigma_S \quad (27)$$

In our model, we impose $\tilde{\varphi} = \varphi(d_{DDL})$, i.e. we assume that the bulk potential is reached at the boundary 1. We can thus use Eqs. 26 and 27 to calculate the potential difference between electrode and boundary 1 from the charge density:

$$\varphi(d_{DDL}) - \varphi_M = -\frac{2RT}{F} \sinh^{-1} \left(-\frac{\sigma_S}{\sqrt{8RT\varepsilon_r\varepsilon_0\tilde{C}_F}} \right) - \frac{d_{OHP}}{\varepsilon_r\varepsilon_0} \sigma_S \quad (28)$$

3.3 Analytical expression for the accumulated charge

We define the adsorption integrals Γ_i of the i -th chemical species as:

$$\Gamma_i = \int_1 [C_i(x) - \tilde{C}_i] dx \quad (29)$$

where \tilde{C} is the bulk concentration, evaluated on boundary 1, i.e. $\tilde{C} = C_i(d_{DDL})$. The adsorption integrals can be analytically calculated based on the theory sketched in Sect. 3.2. Results are reported in literature [9] for solutions containing two ion species. The calculation for our case, with three different ions, is reported in Supporting Information, Sect. S2. The result is the following:

$$\Gamma_i = \tilde{C}_i \frac{1}{F} \sqrt{\frac{2\varepsilon_r\varepsilon_0RT}{\tilde{C}_F}} \left[1 - \exp \left\{ -z_i \frac{F}{2RT} [\tilde{\varphi} - \varphi(x = 0)] \right\} \right] \quad (30)$$

It is worth noting that the adsorption integrals are related to the charge of the DDL, σ_S :

$$\sigma_S = \int_1 \rho(x) dx = \int_1 F \sum_i z_i C_i dx = F \sum_i z_i \Gamma_i \quad (31)$$

The last equality relies on the electroneutrality on boundary 1.

3.4 Analytical formulas expressed as boundary conditions

By performing numerical simulations of the physical system described in Sect. 2, we checked that the analytical equations derived so far actually represent a very good approximation of the behaviour of the system in domain I. We finally aim at removing the simulation of domain I from our calculation: the numerical calculation of the dynamic variables in domain I is substituted by suitable analytical equations, expressed as boundary equations and conditions on boundary 1. The procedure is discussed in this section.

We start by integrating Eq. 5 on domain I:

$$\int_I \frac{dC_i}{dt} dz = \int_I (-\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i + r_i) dz \quad (32)$$

The left-hand side is related to the adsorption integral Γ_i through Eq. 29; according to Eq. 14, the last term on the right-hand side corresponds to G_i ; the integral of $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i$ can be easily calculated, using the boundary condition Eq. 7:

$$\frac{d(\Gamma_i + \tilde{C}_i d_{DDL})}{dt} = -\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{J}_i(d_{DDL}) + G_i \quad (33)$$

We multiply times z_i , sum over all the ions, and use Eq. 31 to get:

$$\frac{d\sigma_S}{dt} = -F \sum_i z_i \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{J}_i(d_{DDL}) + F \sum_i z_i G_i \quad (34)$$

We add σ_S as an additional dynamic variable on boundary 1 and we define its time evolution as a boundary equation through Eq. 34, in which the \mathbf{J}_i are defined by Eq. 6 and the G_i are defined by Eq. 17. Since we aim at completely removing the simulation of domain I from our calculation, the procedure to calculate \mathbf{J}_i and G_i must be properly defined, so that it does not rely on quantities inside domain I.

The evaluation of J_i through Eq. 6 is based on the values of the concentrations C_i and of the potential φ around boundary 1. Since the space derivative of C_i appears in Eq. 6, it is not enough to have the value on the boundary 1, however, we can calculate the right-hand-side derivative at boundary 1 based on domain II, even if domain I is removed.

The evaluation of G_i through Eq. 17 is more tricky, because the equation depends on C_i and φ at $x = 0$, i.e. on values inside domain I. We rewrite Eq. (16) as:

$$G_{ox} = k_0 \frac{1 - \exp(-\beta d_{DDL})}{\beta} \left(-C_{ox}^b \exp \left\{ -\alpha \frac{1}{RT} F[\varphi^b - \varphi_M - \Delta\varphi_0] \right\} + C_{red}^b \exp \left\{ (1 - \alpha) \frac{1}{RT} F[\varphi^b - \varphi_M - \Delta\varphi_0] \right\} \right) \quad (35)$$

where $C_{ox}^b = C_{ox}(x = 0)$, $C_{red}^b = C_{red}(x = 0)$, and $\varphi^b = \varphi(x = 0)$. In turn, we calculate φ^b from σ_S (which is a dynamic variable) by using Eq. 28:

$$\varphi^b = \varphi_M + \frac{d_{OHP}}{\varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0} \sigma_S \quad (36)$$

The value φ_M , which appears in the equation, is the imposed potential of the electrode and is assumed to be known. We finally calculate C_i^b , i.e. the concentration at $x = 0$, by using the Boltzmann relation, Eq. 20:

$$C_i^b = \tilde{C}_i \exp \left\{ -\frac{z_i F[\varphi^b - \tilde{\varphi}]}{RT} \right\} \quad (37)$$

The terms appearing in this equation, $\tilde{C}_i = C_i(d_{DDL})$ and $\tilde{\varphi} = \varphi(d_{DDL})$, are the values of the dynamic variables on boundary 1. By this procedure, all the terms needed for calculating σ_S by means of Eq. 34 are evaluated based on quantities in domain II and boundary 1, thus independently of quantities in domain I.

In order to make the equation system complete, in the absence of domain I, it is necessary to devise suitable boundary conditions on boundary 1 for domain II.

The derivation of Eq. 28 relies on the assumption of electro-neutrality in the bulk. In our context, in the case of calculations of the equilibrium thermodynamics of the EDL, “bulk” actually means at $x = d_{DDL}$, at boundary 1; thus, we impose the electroneutrality as a Dirichlet condition on boundary 1:

$$C_F(d_{DDL}) = C_{ox}(d_{DDL}) + C_K(d_{DDL}) \quad (38)$$

Moreover, we impose a condition on the flux, derived from Eq. 33:

$$\mathbf{J}_i(d_{DDL}) = \tilde{\mathbf{J}}_i \quad (39)$$

where

$$\tilde{\mathbf{J}}_i = \left[-\frac{d\Gamma_i}{dt} - \frac{dC_i(d_{DDL})}{dt} d_{DDL} + G_i \right] \mathbf{n} \quad (40)$$

is the flux in the bulk near the DDL.

The total number of boundary conditions for concentrations, Eqs. 38 and 39, is five, thus exceeding the number of the dynamic variables, the four concentrations; however, only four conditions are independent. This can be shown by multiplying Eq. 40 times z_i , summing over i , and imposing the electroneutrality, Eq. 38. The result equals Eq. 34, which is already imposed. The added boundary conditions are thus consistent with each other.

Finally, the Dirichlet boundary condition for φ is obtained from Eq. 26, rewritten as:

$$\varphi(d_{DDL}) = \varphi^b - \frac{2RT}{F} \sinh^{-1} \left(-\frac{\sigma_S}{\sqrt{8RT\varepsilon_r\varepsilon_0\tilde{C}_F}} \right) \quad (41)$$

In the semi-analytical model, the current is calculated with the following procedure.

Eq. 11 is rewritten using Eq. 14 to express the integral of r_{ox} in terms of G_{ox} and using Eq. 31 to express the integral of ρ in terms of σ_M , thus obtaining:

$$i = -\frac{d}{dt}\sigma_S + FG_{ox} \quad (42)$$

3.5 Potential and concentration as a function of the position

It is possible to solve Eq. 23 by separation of variables:

$$\varphi(x) = -\frac{2RT}{F} \ln \left\{ \tanh \left[\sqrt{\frac{\tilde{C}_F}{2RT\varepsilon_r\varepsilon_0}} F(x - x_0) \right] \right\} + \tilde{\varphi} \quad (43)$$

where x_0 is an arbitrary constant, which is defined by imposing the potential at the OHP, $\varphi(x = 0) = \varphi^b$:

$$x_0 = -\sqrt{\frac{2RT\varepsilon_r\varepsilon_0}{\tilde{C}_F}} \frac{1}{F} \tanh^{-1} \left(\exp \left\{ -\frac{F}{2RT} [\varphi^b - \tilde{\varphi}] \right\} \right) \quad (44)$$

By using the value of $\varphi(x)$ calculated with Eq. 43, it is then possible to calculate the concentrations C_i at any position x by means of the Boltzmann equation, Eq. 20.

The variables defined on boundary 1, used for the application of the semi-analytical method, are summarized in Supporting Information, Sect. S1, Table S2.

4 Numerical simulation

We solved the partial differential equations of the full physical model and of the semi-analytical model by means of a finite element method, using COMSOL [10], a multi-scale, multi-physics modelling software. We considered the physical parameters for ferrocene ethanol and ferrocenium ethanol (Fe^+/Fe^0) solutions, with potassium fluoride supporting electrolyte.

The parameters of the model are reported in Table 1. The COMSOL numerical and semi-analytical models are freely available (see the "Data Availability Statement" section). The correspondence between the mathematical symbols used in this paper and the COMSOL files is reported in Supporting Information, Sect. S3.

The finite element mesh is the same as the one used in the previous reference [4]. The simulations have been performed based on backward differentiation formula. The relative and absolute tolerances were taken 10^{-4} and 10^{-6} , respectively.

The initial concentration of the ions is uniform at $t = 0$, and is set to the values $C_{ox,0}$, $C_{red,0}$, $C_{K,0}$, and $C_{F,0}$, for the oxidized and reduced species, and for the positive and negative ion of the supporting electrolyte, respectively.

The system was controlled by imposing a cell potential, ΔE , between the working and counter electrodes, $\Delta E = E_{WE} - E_{CE}$; the working electrode potential, E_{WE} , and the current, i , were measured and analyzed.

The simulation is composed by two consecutive stages. In the first, the potential ΔE is kept constant (equal to 0, in the simulations reported in this paper), in order to reach a stationary state; this first stage lasts for 200 s, with a maximum time step of 1 s. After this equilibration stage, we apply a sinusoidal signal with amplitude 10 mV at a frequency f for a time duration of $5/f$ with a maximum time step of $0.005/f$. The simulations were repeated for 50 different frequencies between 1 Hz to 100 kHz.

For each frequency f , the electrode potential, E_{WE} , and the current, i , are monitored during the application of the sinusoidal wave. The Fourier components at frequency f of E_{WE} and i are then calculated. The impedance Z is eventually calculated according to the equation:

$$Z = \frac{\int \exp(-2\pi i f t) E_{WE}(t) dt}{\int \exp(-2\pi i f t) i(t) dt} \quad (45)$$

In order to better investigate the features of the DDL, other quantities are also analysed in a similar way, including the concentration of the various species at boundary 1, $C_i(d_{DDL})$, the bulk concentration near the DDL, \tilde{C}_i , and the potential difference across the DDL, $\varphi(0) - \varphi(d_{DDL})$. Calling $\gamma(t)$ the quantity under analysis, its frequency response $\Xi[\gamma]$, with respect to the working electrode potential, at frequency f , is defined as:

$$\Xi[\gamma] = \frac{\int \exp(-2\pi ift)\gamma(t)dt}{\int \exp(-2\pi ift)E_{WE}(t)dt} \quad (46)$$

By repeating the calculation at the various frequencies, the dependence of the impedance $Z(f)$ and of the response $\Xi[\gamma](f)$ on f are finally obtained.

5 Results

We performed tests with four different solutions:

- Solution **10 / 500 mM** (redox couple, high concentration): $C_{ox,0} = C_{red,0}=10$ mol/m³ and $C_{K,0} = C_{F,0}=500$ mol/m³, **green** in graphs;
- Solution **1 / 50 mM** (redox couple, low concentration): $C_{ox,0} = C_{red,0}=1$ mol/m³ and $C_{K,0} = C_{F,0}=50$ mol/m³, **red** in graphs;
- Solution **0 / 500 mM** (no redox couple, high concentration): Without redox couple, $C_{K,0} = C_{F,0}=500$ mol/m³, **magenta** in graphs;
- Solution **0 / 10 mM** (no redox couple, low concentration): Without redox couple, $C_{K,0} = C_{F,0}=10$ mol/m³, **blue** in graphs.

Fig. 2: Impedance spectra of the solutions without redox couple. Squares and circles represent the real part and the opposite of imaginary part of the impedance, respectively, calculated with the semi-analytical method. Lines are the results of the numerical model. The lower panel shows the relative discrepancy between the (complex) impedances calculated with the numerical and semi-analytical models.

The impedance spectra for the two solutions without redox couple are shown in Fig. 2. It can be noticed that the results of the semi-analytical model (squares and circles) are remarkably similar to the results of the numerical model (lines); the good quality of the results are also confirmed by the plot of the relative error (lower panel). The real part is constant with respect to the frequency: it represents the uncompensated series resistance, which depends on the salt concentration. The imaginary part shows a capacitive behaviour, $1/(i\omega C)$. The small discrepancy between the imaginary part of the impedance (circles) for the two solutions is due to the different thickness of the DDL in the two cases. This feature is properly calculated by the semi-analytical model, showing that it is able to capture the features of the DDL without the need of a numerical calculation.

Fig. 3: Nyquist impedance spectra of the solutions with redox couple.

Squares are the results of the semi-analytical model. Lines are the results of the numerical model.

The Nyquist plot of the impedance spectra, for the two solutions with redox couple, are shown in Fig. 3. The two impedances are normalized by multiplying times the concentration, in order to get graphs of similar size. Even in this case, the results of the semi-analytical model are remarkably similar to the results of the numerical

model. The typical shape shows a semi-circle (resulting from the charge-transfer resistance and DDL capacitance) and the Warburg tail.

Fig. 4: Impedance spectra of the solutions with redox couple. Squares and circles represent the real part and the opposite of imaginary part of the

impedance, respectively, calculated with the semi-analytical method.

Green and red lines are the results of the numerical model. The lower panel shows the relative discrepancy between the (complex) impedances calculated with the numerical and semi-analytical models.

These facts can be also seen in Fig. 4, which reports the frequency dependence of the impedance. In the lower panel of Fig. 4, the relative error is also shown. It is less than 1% for all the analysed range.

The results of both the numerical and semi-analytical model can be fitted with a Randles circuit. We tested in particular the 1 / 50 mM solution. The quality of the two fits is comparable and the discrepancy between the fitted Randles circuit and the simulated data is of the order of 0.1%, which is one decade less than the discrepancy between the two models. The two sets of parameters, fitted to the semi-analytical and numerical models, are also quite similar: the largest discrepancy appears on the charge transfer resistance and is around 1%, i.e. of the same order of magnitude of the relative discrepancy between the two simulated spectra.

In order to better probe the precision of the semi-analytical model, we analysed other quantities, which characterize the DDL. One of them is the potential across the DDL, $\varphi(0) - \varphi(d_{DDL})$. Its frequency response $\Delta(f)$ with respect to the working electrode potential, at frequency f , is defined according to Eq. 46 as:

$$\Delta = \frac{\int \exp(-2\pi i f t) [\varphi(0, t) - \varphi(d_{DDL}, t)] dt}{\int \exp(-2\pi i f t) E_{WE}(t) dt} \quad (47)$$

Fig. 5: Frequency response of potential across the DDL, $\Delta(f)$, for two solutions. Squares and circles represent the real part and the opposite of imaginary part of the response, calculated with the semi-analytical

method. Lines are the results of the numerical model. The lower panel shows the relative discrepancy between the (complex) responses calculated with the numerical and semi-analytical models.

The frequency response $\Delta(f)$ of the potential across the DDL is reported in Fig. 5. The agreement of the semi-analytical model with the numerical model is very good. The discrepancy increases for high frequency, where the assumption that the EDL is at thermodynamic equilibrium tends to be violated. For the 0 / 10 mM solution, two regimes can be observed, roughly below and above 4 kHz. At low frequencies, $\Delta(f)$ is almost constant and real: the potential across the DDL is a fixed fraction of the of the oscillation of the electrode potential, E_{WE} . At high frequencies, the resistance of the electrolyte becomes increasingly predominant, leading to the decrease of the fraction of voltage that falls across the DDL. In the case of the solution 10 / 500 mM, the transition is close to the right-hand-side of the frequency range; the almost horizontal branch of the imaginary part, at low frequencies, is attributed to the discharge of the EDL by the redox reaction. All these phenomena are properly calculated by the semi-analytical model.

Fig. 6: Frequency response of concentration of K^+ at boundary 1, $\chi_K^1(f)$, for two solutions. Squares and circles represent the modulus and the phase of the response, calculated with the semi-analytical method. Lines are the results of the numerical model. The lower panel shows the relative discrepancy between the (complex) responses calculated with the numerical and semi-analytical models.

Another interesting quantity, which characterizes the DDL, is the concentration at boundary 1, $C_i(x = d_{DDL})$, i.e. the concentration on a plane that can be considered as the solution bulk for the DDL but is still close enough to the electrode to be affected by the salt capture taking place when the DDL is charged. The frequency response $\chi_i^1(f)$ of this quantity, with respect to the working electrode potential, at frequency f , is defined according to Eq. 46 as:

$$\chi_i^1 = \frac{\int \exp(-2\pi ift) C_i(x=d_{DDL}) dt}{\int \exp(-2\pi ift) E_{WE}(t) dt} \quad (48)$$

The graph of the frequency response $\chi_K^1(f)$, for $C_K(x = d_{DDL})$, is reported in Fig. 6. At high frequencies, a quite visible difference between the results of the semi-analytical and numerical models can be noticed. It is attributed to the violation of the assumption that the DDL is in thermodynamic equilibrium, due to the fast variations of potential. The discrepancy can be considered acceptable, since it does not affect the impedance results. Indeed, the violation takes place in a frequency range in which the impedance is mostly determined by the interplay between charge transfer resistance, EDL resistance, and electrolyte resistance, while the diffusion effects, influenced by the concentration, have a minor role.

Fig. 7: Frequency response of concentration of K^+ and F^- at boundary 1, $\chi_K^1(f)$ and $\chi_F^1(f)$, and of bulk concentrations, $\tilde{\chi}_K(f) = \tilde{\chi}_F(f)$, for the 0 / 10 mM solution. The symbols represent the real part of the responses $\chi_K^1(f)$ and $\chi_F^1(f)$, calculated with the semi-analytical method. The solid lines are the results of the numerical model. The dotted line is the response of the bulk concentrations, $\tilde{\chi}_K(f) = \tilde{\chi}_F(f)$. The lower panel shows the relative discrepancy between the (complex) responses $\chi_K^1(f)$ and $\chi_F^1(f)$ calculated with the numerical and semi-analytical models.

It is important to notice that, for the semi-analytical case, the concentration $C_K(x = d_{DDL})$ on boundary 1, shown in Fig. 7, is calculated by means of the procedure shown in Sect. 3.5. It is interesting to analyse the frequency response of \tilde{C}_i , the quantity that is considered the bulk concentration in the analytical formulas describing the EDL. According to Eq. 46, it is defined as:

$$\tilde{\chi}_i = \frac{\int \exp(-2\pi i f t) \tilde{C}_i dt}{\int \exp(-2\pi i f t) E_{WE}(t) dt} \quad (49)$$

The comparison between the responses of the concentrations of positive and negative charges in $x = d_{DDL}$, $\chi_K^1(f)$ and $\chi_F^1(f)$, and the response of the bulk concentrations, $\tilde{\chi}_K(f) = \tilde{\chi}_F(f)$, is reported in Fig. 7. It can be noticed that the concentrations of the two oppositely charged ions in $x = d_{DDL}$ significantly deviate from the bulk values, due to the electric field of the DDL, even if d_{DDL} is much larger than the characteristic thickness of the DDL, λ : actually, the deviation from 0 of the two values is very small and the effect can only be seen when $\tilde{\chi}_K(f)$, and $\tilde{\chi}_F(f)$ become negligible.

6 Conclusion

We presented a method for numerically calculate the time evolution of an electrochemical system, including a supporting electrolyte and a redox couple. The

phenomena that are taken into consideration are the redox reactions, the diffusion and the migration of the ions, and the effects of electrical field. The EDL with a DDL is thus thoroughly described by our equations.

The method is based on the numerical calculation with finite elements for the bulk of the solution, while the region very close to the electrode is described by analytical equations, expressed as boundary conditions for the solution bulk. The method works for redox couples in which the reduced and oxidized species have charge 0 and +1 with respect to the electron charge, e.g. ferrocene / ferrocenium. Extensions to other charges is possible by developing suitable mathematical expressions.

The example of application reported in this paper is to a cell with a couple of plane parallel electrodes, such that the system is described by a system of differential equations with one space variable (one dimensional). Extension to different geometries is quite easy.

The method is based on two main assumptions: i) the DDL is in thermodynamic equilibrium, at least with a thin slab of solution near the electrode; ii) the solution bulk is electroneutral. We showed that the method is accurate within the limits imposed by these assumptions.

In general, it is not possible to analytically solve the differential equations describing these physical systems and numerical solutions, based on finite element methods, are needed. Such calculations require to cover a large range of lengths, from the macroscopic ones, which describe the diffusion in the bulk, down to the scale of

nanometers, in order to properly describe the DDL. This requirement is computationally expensive. Our method enables a calculation without bringing the mesh size down to the scale of the nanometers, by describing the EDL as an analytical equation imposed as a boundary condition. The method thus strongly decreases the needed computational resources.

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Author contribution statement

FLM conceived the idea. FT and DB developed the equations and the method. FT performed the numerical and semi-analytical calculations. DB defined the tests to be performed, prepared the graphs, and discussed the results. FLM and DB wrote the paper.

Data Availability Statement

The COMSOL models (fully numerical and semi-analytical) and the data used to produce all the graphs reported in this paper can be downloaded from the Materials Cloud Archive, DOI: 10.24435/materialscloud:5e-39 .

List of symbols

Symbol	Definition	Unit
C^b	Concentration at $x = 0$	mol/m ³
$C_i(x)$	Concentration of species i at coordinate x	mol/m ³
$C_{i,0}$	Initial concentration of species i	M
\tilde{C}_i	Concentration of species i in bulk near DDL	mol/m ³
D_i	Diffusion coefficient of species i	m ² /s
E_{CE}	Potential of the counter electrode with respect to reference	V
E_{WE}	Potential of the working electrode with respect to reference	V
F	Faraday constant	C/mol
G_i	Generation of species i	mol/m ³ /s
\tilde{J}_i	Flux of species i in the bulk near DDL	mol/m ² /s
$J_i(x)$	Flux of species i at coordinate x	mol/m ² /s
L	Distance between electrodes	m
\mathbf{n}	Unit vector directed along x axis	
R	Gas constant	J/K/mol
T	Temperature	K
$Z(f)$	Impedance	Ω
d_{DDL}	Thickness of electrical double layer domain	m
d_{OHP}	Length of outer Helmholtz layer	m
f	Frequency	Hz
i	Current density	A/m ²
k_0	Reaction constant	1/s
$k_{ox}(x)$	First-order rate constant of oxidation reaction	m/s
$k_{red}(x)$	First-order rate constant of reduction reaction	m/s
$r_i(x)$	Reaction rate of species species i at coordinate x	mol/m ³ /s
z_i	Charge of species i	
$\Delta\varphi_0$	Standard potential of the redox reaction	V
ΔE	Potential difference between working and counter-electrode	V
Γ_i	Adsorption integral of species i	mol/m ²
α	Transfer coefficient	
β	Inverse of the tunnelling distance	1/m
ε_0	Permittivity of vacuum	F/m
ε_r	Relative permittivity	
φ^b	Potential at $x = 0$	V

$\varphi(x)$	Potential at coordinate x	V
φ_M	Potential of the electrode, $\varphi(-d_{OHP})$	V
$\tilde{\varphi}$	Potential in bulk near DDL	V
λ	Characteristic length of diffuse double layer	M
$\rho(x)$	Charge density at coordinate x	C/m ³
σ_M	Charge density on the surface of the electrode	C/m ²
σ_S	Charge density in the diffuse double layer	C/m ²
$\chi_i^1(f)$	Frequency response of $C_i(x = d_{DDL})$	mM/V
$\tilde{\chi}_i(f)$	Frequency response of \tilde{C}_i	mM/V

List of acronyms

Acronym	Definition
EDL	Electric double layer
DDL	Diffuse double layer
OHP	Outer Helmholtz plane

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